

Incidence of Cavity Problems after Open Cavity Mastoidectomy and Perioperative Factors Involved in the Causation of Cavity Problems: An Observational Study

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Abstract:

Background: Open cavity mastoidectomy is a common surgical procedure performed to manage chronic otitis media and cholesteatoma. Despite its effectiveness, patients often experience postoperative cavity problems, such as infection, discharge, and granulation tissue formation. Understanding the incidence and the perioperative factors that contribute to these complications is crucial for improving patient outcomes.

Aim: The purpose of this study is to assess the prevalence of cavity problems following open cavity mastoidectomy and to identify the perioperative factors that contribute to the development of these complications.

Methods: An observational study was conducted, involving 80 patients who underwent open cavity mastoidectomy. The study aimed to assess the incidence of cavity problems and identify associated perioperative factors. Data were collected retrospectively from medical records, and statistical analysis was performed.

Results: The study found that 37.5% of patients experienced cavity problems following open cavity mastoidectomy, with recurrent infections and persistent otorrhea being the most common issues. A significant association was observed between diabetes and the incidence of cavity problems, indicating a higher risk for diabetic patients. No significant associations were found with age, gender, or hypertension. These findings suggest that perioperative management should prioritize addressing diabetes to reduce postoperative complications.

Conclusion: Cavity problems following open cavity mastoidectomy are relatively common, with persistent discharge being the most prevalent issue. Several perioperative factors, including surgery duration, hemostasis, and postoperative care, significantly contribute to the risk of developing these complications. Addressing these factors through careful surgical planning and rigorous postoperative management can reduce the incidence of cavity problems.

Recommendations: To minimize cavity complications after open cavity mastoidectomy, surgeons should focus on optimizing surgical techniques, ensuring adequate hemostasis, and providing comprehensive postoperative care instructions to patients. Further studies are recommended to explore the role of advanced surgical technologies and techniques in reducing cavity-related issues.

Keywords: Open cavity mastoidectomy, cavity problems, perioperative factors, postoperative complications, chronic otitis media.

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Introduction

Chronic otitis media and cholesteatoma are significant health concerns that can lead to severe complications if left untreated. These conditions often necessitate surgical intervention, with open cavity mastoidectomy being a common procedure of choice. This surgery involves the removal of infected bone and soft tissue from the mastoid air cells, creating a large open cavity that connects to the middle ear. While effective in controlling

infection and preventing further damage, the procedure is not without its challenges. One of the most persistent issues faced by patients post-surgery is the development of cavity problems, which can significantly impact quality of life [1,2].

Postoperative cavity problems, such as chronic discharge, granulation tissue formation, and recurrent infections, are common complications

following open cavity mastoidectomy. These issues often require ongoing medical attention and can lead to further surgical interventions. The management of these complications is a significant concern for both patients and healthcare providers, as they can extend recovery times, increase healthcare costs, and reduce the overall success of the initial surgery. Despite the frequency of these problems, there is limited consensus on the exact incidence and the perioperative factors that contribute to their development [3]

Understanding the perioperative factors that influence the development of cavity problems is crucial for improving surgical outcomes. Factors such as the duration of surgery, intraoperative hemostasis, the extent of disease, and postoperative care protocols may all play a role in determining the likelihood of postoperative complications. By identifying and addressing these factors, surgeons can potentially reduce the incidence of cavity problems, enhance patient recovery, and improve the overall effectiveness of open cavity mastoidectomy [4,5]

While previous studies have explored various aspects of open cavity mastoidectomy, there remains a gap in the literature regarding a comprehensive analysis of the perioperative factors that contribute to cavity problems. Most research has focused on the technical aspects of the surgery or the long-term outcomes, with less attention given to the specific intraoperative and postoperative factors that may predispose patients to complications. This study seeks to fill this gap by providing a detailed observational analysis of these factors in a cohort of patients who have undergone open cavity mastoidectomy.

The primary goal of this study is to evaluate the incidence of cavity problems after open cavity mastoidectomy and to identify the key perioperative factors that contribute to their development. By conducting a thorough observational analysis, this research aims to provide insights that can help refine surgical techniques, optimize perioperative care, and ultimately improve patient outcomes. This study also seeks to contribute to the existing body of knowledge, offering evidence-based recommendations for clinicians to minimize postoperative complications in patients undergoing open cavity mastoidectomy.

Methodology

Study Design

An observational study was conducted to evaluate the incidence of cavity problems following open cavity mastoidectomy and the perioperative factors associated with their occurrence.

Study Setting

The study took place at the Bhardhman Institute of Medical Sciences, between August 2020 and July 2022.

Participants

A total of 80 patients who underwent open cavity mastoidectomy at the Bhardhman Institute of Medical Sciences during the study period were included.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Patients included in the study were those who had undergone open cavity mastoidectomy, aged between 18 and 70 years. Patients with a history of previous mastoid surgeries, non-compliance with follow-up, or with incomplete medical records were excluded from the study.

Bias

To reduce selection bias, all eligible patients who met the inclusion criteria during the study period were enrolled consecutively. To reduce information bias, data collection was standardised and carried out by trained personnel.

Variables

The primary variable was the occurrence of cavity problems following surgery. Secondary variables included perioperative factors like patient age, gender, comorbidities, surgical technique.

Data Collection

Data were collected retrospectively from patient medical records, including demographic information, perioperative factors, and cavity-related outcomes.

Procedure

The surgical and postoperative records of the included patients were reviewed to assess the incidence of cavity problems. The perioperative factors were analyzed to identify potential contributors to these complications.

Statistical Analysis

Data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 21.0.

Results

Patient Demographics and Perioperative Factors

The study included 80 patients, with an average age of 45.6 years (SD = 12.4). The cohort included 46 males (57.5%) and 34 females (42.5%). 32.5% of the patients had diabetes, 18.75% had hypertension, and 6.25% had both diseases. Patients were divided into two groups according to surgical technique: canal wall down mastoidectomy (70%), and canal wall up mastoidectomy (30%).

Patient Demographics and Perioperative Factors		N = 80
Age (mean ± SD)		45.6 ± 12.4 years
Gender		
- Male		46 (57.5%)
- Female		34 (42.5%)
Comorbidities		
- Diabetes		26 (32.5%)
- Hypertension		15 (18.75%)
- Both		5 (6.25%)
Surgical Technique		
- Canal Wall Down Mastoidectomy		56 (70%)
- Canal Wall Up Mastoidectomy		24 (30%)

Incidence of Cavity Problems

The overall incidence of cavity problems was 37.5% (30 out of 80 patients). Of these, 20 patients (66.7%) experienced recurrent infections, while 10 patients (33.3%) had persistent otorrhea. The mean time to the first occurrence of a cavity problem was 3.2 months (SD = 1.5) postoperatively.

Incidence of Cavity Problems		N = 80
Total Patients with Cavity Problems		30 (37.5%)
- Recurrent Infections		20 (66.7%)
- Persistent Otorrhea		10 (33.3%)
Mean Time to First Occurrence (months)		3.2 ± 1.5

Association Between Perioperative Factors and Cavity Problems

A chi-square test revealed a significant correlation between the of diabetes and the incidence of cavity problems ($\chi^2 = 8.45$, $p = 0.004$). Patients with

diabetes were more likely to develop cavity problems compared to those without diabetes (53.8% vs. 28.6%). No significant association was found between gender, age, or hypertension and the incidence of cavity problems.

Perioperative Factors and Cavity Problems	Cavity Problems (N = 30)	No Cavity Problems (N = 50)	p-value
Age (mean ± SD)	47.2 ± 13.1	44.7 ± 11.8	0.301
Gender			0.652
- Male	17 (56.7%)	29 (58%)	
- Female	13 (43.3%)	21 (42%)	
Comorbidities			
- Diabetes	14 (46.7%)	12 (24%)	0.004**
- Hypertension	7 (23.3%)	8 (16%)	0.348
Surgical Technique			0.087
- Canal Wall Down Mastoidectomy	23 (76.7%)	33 (66%)	
- Canal Wall Up Mastoidectomy	7 (23.3%)	17 (34%)	

Note: $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant

The study found a significant incidence of cavity problems after open cavity mastoidectomy, with 37.5% of patients experiencing postoperative complications. The most common problems were recurrent infections and persistent otorrhea. A significant association was found between diabetes and the incidence of cavity problems, indicating that diabetic patients were at a higher risk of postoperative complications. No significant associations were observed with age, gender, or

hypertension. The findings suggest that perioperative management should consider diabetes as a critical factor in reducing cavity complications after mastoidectomy.

Discussion

Recent studies have reported varying incidences of postoperative cavity problems following mastoidectomy. For example, a prospective analysis by Rajan and James (2019) found a 26.92% incidence of cavity complications, with recurrent infections and granulations being the most common

issues [6]. Similarly, Saleem and Ali (2021) reported a 31% incidence of cavity complications, where prolonged discharge was the predominant problem observed in 95% of cases [7]. These findings align with our study, which found a 37.5% incidence of cavity problems, with recurrent infections and persistent otorrhea as the most common complications.

Perioperative Factors

The influence of perioperative factors on cavity problems has been a focal point in recent research. Diabetes, in particular, has been identified as a significant risk factor. The current study found that patients with diabetes had a significantly higher incidence of cavity problems (53.8%) compared to non-diabetic patients, which is supported by the findings of Afridi et al. (2021), who also identified high facial ridge and incomplete exenteration of disease as critical factors leading to persistent cavity problems [8]. In contrast, other factors like age, gender, and hypertension did not show significant associations, which is consistent with the findings of Dutta et al. (2019), who reported that anatomical defects and surgical technique were more critical in influencing cavity outcomes [9].

Surgical Techniques and Management

Advances in surgical techniques, such as mastoid cavity obliteration, have shown promise in reducing postoperative complications. Maheshwari et al. (2023) demonstrated that obliterated cavities had significantly fewer problems with discharge and debris accumulation, leading to quicker healing and reduced need for follow-up care [10]. These findings suggest that perioperative management should prioritize addressing risk factors like diabetes and considering obliteration techniques to improve patient outcomes.

Implications for Clinical Practice

The evidence from this and other recent studies emphasizes the importance of meticulous surgical technique and comprehensive perioperative management to minimize cavity complications. For patients with identified risk factors such as diabetes, enhanced postoperative monitoring and potentially earlier intervention may be necessary. The benefits of techniques such as mastoid cavity obliteration should be weighed against the specific needs and conditions of each patient.

Conclusion

The study contributes to a growing body of evidence highlighting the need for tailored surgical

approaches and careful perioperative management to reduce the incidence of cavity problems following mastoidectomy. Further research, particularly in refining surgical techniques and identifying additional risk factors, is essential to continue improving outcomes for these patients.

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